

Spectrophotometric Investigations on Chelate Formation in Nickel (II)-6-Carboxyl-3'-Methyl-6'-Hydroxy-Azobenzene-4-Sulphonic Acid (CMHAS)- System

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CMHAS is proposed as a new reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of Ni(II). The present communication describes the synthesis of CMHAS and the results of a study regarding the complex formation of Ni(II) with CMHAS.

Experimental

Spectrophotometric measurements were made on Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer using silica cuvettes of 1 cm path length. All chemicals used were of AR grade.

Synthesis of CMHAS: 5-sulphoanthranilic acid¹ was diazotised² and immediately coupled with *p*-cresol in alkaline medium. The product was isolated as its barium salt and converted into sodium salt by Na₂SO₄. It was recrystallised from alcohol water mixture. The dye was finally purified by making it free acid and was then recrystallised repeatedly from 50% ethanol. Its purity was checked by potentiometric titration, thin layer chromatography and by elemental analysis.

Nickel perchlorate solution was used. The pH of the solutions were adjusted with NaOH and HClO₄. Red coloured water soluble complex was formed instantaneously and the colour intensity was found to be independent of the order of addition of reagents.

Results and Discussion

The acid dissociation of CMHAS may be represented as :

Spectrophotometric methods^{3,4} exhibited pK₁ and pK₂ as 3.53 and 10.36 respectively. The values of pK₁ and pK₂ by potentiometric method^{5,6} at an initial ionic strength of 0.04 are found to be 3.51 and 10.18 respectively. The -SO₃H group might be dissociating at lower pH value thus not permitting its pK determination under the present conditions.

Absorption spectra of the ligand shows the shifts in λ_{max} with pH. From pH 1.0 to 10.0 the λ_{max} was at 332 nm and from 11.0 to 12.0 the λ_{max} was at 332 and 480 nm.

Vosburgh and Cooper's method⁷ showed the existence of one complex giving the maxima 500 nm at pH 7.5. No effect of temperature (5°-95°) was observed on the absorbance values (by keeping the

volume constant). The chelate was stable for more than 120 hr and in the pH range 7.0-10.0 (when the ratio of the metal : ligand was 1 : 4).

The composition of the chelate was established to be 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) by the method of continuous variations⁸, mole ratio method⁹, and slope ratio method¹⁰. Stability constant was calculated using Janssen's method¹¹ with suitable modification¹². The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANT OF NICKEL(II) CHELATE

pK ₁ = 3.53	pH = 7.50		
pK ₂ = 10.36	E ₁ = 7140		
E _L = 1560	Wave length = 500 nm.		
Ionic strength (μ) = 0.1 (NaClO ₄)			
S.No.	T _M × 10 ⁶	Absorbance	
1	0.0	0.078	E ₂
2	0.5	0.088	23140
3	1.0	0.098	23130
4	2.0	0.109	
5	15.0	0.220	Log K ₂
6	20.0	0.268	10.287
7	25.0	0.317	10.553
			10.729
8	60.0	0.344	Log K ₁
9	70.0	0.349	12.619
10	80.0	0.352	12.599
11	90.0	0.354	12.653
12	100.0	0.356	12.756
13	250.0	0.357	

Average value of Log K₁ = 12.656.
Average value of Log K₂ = 10.490.

Fig. 1. Absorbance spectra of the ligand and the complex. Curve A—[CMHAS] 5 × 10⁻⁵M + Ni(II) 2 × 10⁻⁴M at 7.5 pH. Curve B—[CMHAS] 5 × 10⁻⁵M at 7.5 pH.

Analytical Applications :

Six fold excess of reagent was required for maximum colour intensity. Beer's law holds good in the range 0.5-2.8 ppm and the effective photometric range was found to be 0.7-2.1 ppm of Ni(II). The average molar absorptivity at pH 7.5 and at λ_{max}

500 nm is 7140 with Sandell's sensitivity $0.01 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. The average and relative standard deviations were 0.005 and 0.7 per cent respectively.

The ions which do not interfere at all concentrations are Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , ClO_4^- , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- , F^- , SO_4^{2-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, PO_4^{3-} , $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6^{2-}$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7^{3-}$, Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Ag^+ , Sn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , and Pd^{2+} . The ions which seriously interfere are Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} (± 2 percent in absorbance value was arbitrarily taken as an interference).

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Studies in Terpenes : Part XXXIX : *m*-Menth-1-en-8-ol, A constituent of Wallach's Sylveterpineol

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THE two *m*-terpineols comprising Wallach's sylveterpineol have been declared as *m*-menth-6-en-8-ol (1) and *m*-menth-1-en-8-ol (2) based on the examination of oxidation products.^{1,2} Spectroscopic data backing structure (1) were presented by us earlier.^{3,4} We would like to report now further evidence which sheds light on the isomeric constituent (2).

Repetition of the esterification of Wallach's sylveterpineol [b.p. $90^\circ\text{--}92^\circ$ (5 mm)] with *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride according to published procedure⁵ gave a benzoate, m.p. 66° , $(\alpha)_D^{30} + 38.4^\circ$ (*c* 1.2, CHCl_3). (Found : C, 67.61; H, 7.17; N, 5.15. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires : C, 67.26; H, 6.99; N, 4.62%). Saponification was effected by heating a mixture of the ester (10 g), ether (25 ml), methanol (70 ml) and potassium hydroxide (7 g) for 1 hr; usual work-up followed by steam distillation afforded an oil (4.6 g), b.p. $88.5^\circ\text{--}92.5^\circ$ (5 mm), $n_D^{20} + 1.4814$, d_{30}^{30} 0.9306, $(\alpha)_D^{30} + 46.24^\circ$ [Lit.⁵ b.p. 84° (3 mm)], n_D^{20} 1.4838, d_4^{20} 0.9373, $(\alpha)_D^{20} + 46.20^\circ$]. Thin layer chromatography [adsorbent : Silica gel G; developer : benzene-methanol (10 : 1); indicator : vanillin (5%) in concd. sulphuric acid] disclosed that the oil contained two components with R_f 0.62 and 0.52, of which the former R_f was identified as due to (1) by co-chromatography with a genuine sample. A homogeneous specimen of the required constituent was prepared from the oil by gas-liquid chromatography on a 15 ft column of 20% Silicone oil—DC 550 on Chromosorb-W, 60–80 mesh, temp. 165° , hydrogen pressure 15 p.s.i. utilising Aerograph A 90-P₃ Model; R_f 0.56 (Found : C, 77.95; H, 11.50. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{17}\text{OH}$ requires : C, 77.87; H, 11.76%). $\gamma_{\text{max}}^{\text{neat}}$ 3400 and 1150 cm^{-1} , ($\rightarrow$ C—OH), 1375 and 1365 cm^{-1} , [(CH_3)₂C <, doublet] and 1667 and 820 cm^{-1} (> C = CH—).

Proof for the structure of the above alcohol as *m*-menth-1-en-8-ol (2) was provided by the 60 MHz PMR spectra from CDCl_3 (Fig. 1). The C₉ and C₁₀ methyl protons featured as singlet at δ 1.20 and

Fig. 1. Partial 60 MHz PMR spectra of *m*-menth-1-en-8-ol.

the C₁ methyl protons as singlet at δ 1.66. The ring proton at C₂ was visible as a broad singlet at δ 5.40 (curve a). Irradiation at δ 5.40 did not influence the high field pattern in any significant manner. In particular the peak at δ 1.66. In the reverse experiment, however, the broad featureless signal at δ 5.40 sharpened up to something like a six-line pattern, doublet of triplet (curve b) which one would expect due to coupling to protons in positions 3 and 6.